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Abstract

“Baby Bust” is a surprising phenomenon in the most of the developed countries across the world especially in the European countries. Fertility plays crucial role in Baby Busting which is an important indicator for understanding and determining the population and its pattern of any nation. Higher the fertility, larger the population size and vice versa. Standard fertility rate for balanced deaths and births are 2.1 births per women. If fertility rate is higher than this it will cause to high population but if the fertility rate is lower than 2.1 births per women it can lead to negative trends in population growth. Europe 6th largest continent with 49 countries along with its other territories and dependencies is facing rapid decline in the fertility rate from past few years,, now it has the fertility rate of 1.5 births per women in average, few countries are even less than this. Therefore, present article focus on studying the fertility pattern of European countries, main causes that is leading to decline in the fertility rate and polices adopted by government until now in order to control this. Women empowerment, improved prosperity and health services, greater use of contraceptives, postponing the pregnancy, women’s workforce participation etc. has been responsible for baby busting or declining rate in Europe. The declining fertility rate in Europe will cause the problems of aging population and will reduce the size working age population that will lead unrecoverable slow economic growth and fifth stage of demographic transition in European countries.

Keywords: Baby Bust, Birth rates, Demographic transition, Fertility, Population growth.

Introduction

The fertility pattern of the world changed from the past few years. Fertility plays huge role in understating the future trends in population growth. High fertility rate means high population low fertility means low population. According to Cambridge dictionary “fertility is the quality of being able to produce baby in lifetime.” Means fertility is the ability of producing off-springs or children in their entire lifetime (reproductive years) (Smoak, 2016). It depends on different factors like age, health and so on. It differs from every living being as human produce children, animals produce their babies and plants produce fruits (fertility). The fertility pattern changes from person to person main role played by health and age. Fertility rate started declining from 1950’s drastically. The world population depends on the fertility rate of woman. The world fertility rate in 1950’s is 5.009 births per women (Worlds fertility rate 1950-2021).

But the population is not high as now, because of high rate of deaths at that time. But after industrial revolution the quality of life increased so the number of population is also increased even though the fertility rate is declined. Population plays huge role in effectively using the resources available in that place. So the growth of the nation depends on the population of the country. But the population should be eventually distributed to have balanced and sustainable growth, but more than 35% of population concentrated within two countries itself that is China followed by India. It can be because of the vast differences from country to country in child bearing capacity around the world.

Figure 1

Source: Institute of Health Matrix and Evaluation at the University of Washington

Like Africa has the highest fertility rate with average of 4.7 births per women while some regions of Europe has the lowest rate with 1.6 or 1.3 births per women (Worlds fertility patterns 2015). The fertility rate of today's world is 2.438 births per woman which means 0.41% is declined when compared to 2020 fertility rate (2.448%) (Worlds fertility rate, 1950-2021). For stable population the average births given by woman should be near 2.1 to balance deaths and births (Smoak, 2016).

Natural Fertility decline in countries with large population and high fertility rate, more than 2.1 can be good sign to have the effective and sustainable use of resources. But there are few countries which will show negative trends on the population like the balance between the death and births rates with the decline in fertility rate just like Europe where the fertility rate declined to 1.5 births per women (Recer, 2003). So this paper is focused on understanding the cause and consequences of decreasing fertility rate in the Europe. And Policies, measures adopted for controlling and preventing the effects caused by fertility decline.

Methodology and Data Base

The present academic article is a quantitative exercise based on secondary data extracted from Eurostat's database, World population statistics, Macrotrends and other websites. Besides, some of the other sources like news articles and research papers have been used to supplement our analysis. A graphical representation of fertility rate has been applied in order to analyse the spatial pattern of fertility rate across the study area.

Europe

Europe is the 6th largest continent with 44 countries. Europe constitutes about 2% of the earth surface which is 6.2% of the earth's land area recognized as 10 million square kilometers. Europe is separated with the help of Ural Mountains of Russia and by the Caspian and black seas from Asia at south and from Africa by the Mediterranean Sea (Europe, 2020). It is boarded by Artic Ocean in the north, Atlantic Ocean in the west. According to United Nations Europe consists of 44 countries along with some dependencies and other territories. The list of 44 countries and other territories are included in the table

1- shown below. Other territories and dependencies include channel island, Isle of Man, Gibraltar depended on U.K and Faeroe Islands depended on Denmark (Countries in Europe, 2020).

Table-1 shows the population of Europe country wise of 2019 and 2020 along with fertility

Countries/ Regions	2019 Population	2020 Population	Change	Fertility Growth
Russian Federation	145,872,256	145,934,462	62,206	---
Germany	83,517,045	83,783,942	266,897	+0.31%
United Kingdom	67,530,172	67,886,011	355,839	+0.06%
France	65,129,728	65,273,511	143,783	-0.5%
Italy	60,550,075	60,461,826	-88,249	-0.53%
Spain	46,736,776	46,754,778	18,002	+0.89%
Ukraine	43,993,638	43,733,762	-259,876	-0.14%
Poland	37,887,768	37,846,611	-41,157	-0.7%
Romania	19,364,557	19,237,691	-126,866	+0.37%
Netherlands	17,097,130	17,134,872	37,742	+0.24%
Belgium	11,539,328	11,589,623	50,295	+0.12%
Czechia	10,689,209	10,708,981	19,772	+0.49%
Greece	10,473,455	10,423,054	-50,401	-0.62%
Portugal	10,226,187	10,196,709	-29,478	+1%
Sweden	10,036,379	10,099,265	62,886	-0.110%
Hungary	9,684,679	9,660,351	-24,328	+0.67%
Belarus	9,452,411	9,449,323	-3,088	+0.29%
Austria	8,955,102	9,006,398	51,296	0.59%
Serbia	8,772,235	8,737,371	-34,864	-0.55%
Switzerland	8,591,365	8,654,622	63,257	+0.32%
Bulgaria	7,000,119	6,948,445	-51,674	+0.7%
Denmark	5,771,876	5,792,202	20,326	+0.11%
Finland	5,532,156	5,540,720	8,564	-1.46%
Slovakia	5,457,013	5,459,642	2,629	+0.66%
Norway	5,378,857	5,421,241	42,384	+0.24%
Ireland	4,882,495	4,937,786	55,291	-0.6%
Croatia	4,130,304	4,105,267	-25,037	-0.56%
Republic of Moldova	4,043,263	4,033,963	-9,300	+0.87%
Bosnia & Herzegovina	3,301,000	3,280,819	-20,181	-0.71%
Albania	2,880,917	2,877,797	-3,120	-0.93%
Lithuania	2,759,627	2,722,289	-37,338	+0.36%
North Macedonia	2,083,459	2,083,374	-85	-0.47%
Slovenia	2,078,654	2,078,938	284	+0.44%
Latvia	1,906,743	1,886,198	-20,545	+0.23%
Estonia	1,325,648	1,326,535	887	+0.63%
Montenegro	627,987	628,066	79	-0.11%
Luxembourg	615,729	625,978	10,249	-0.49%
Malta	440,372	441,543	1,171	+0.75%
Iceland	339,031	341,243	2,212	-0.62%
Channel Islands	172,259	173,863	1,604	+0.46%
Isle of Man	84,584	85,033	449	+0.54%
Andorra	77,142	77,265	123	--
Faroe Islands	48,678	48,863	185	- 1%
Monaco	38,964	39,242	278	-0.41%
Liechtenstein	38,019	38,128	109	--
San Marino	33,860	33,931	71	--
Gibraltar	33,701	33,691	-10	-0.90%
Holy See	799	801	2	-

Europe

747,182,751

747,636,026

453,275

-

Source: <https://statisticstimes.com/demographics/european-countries-by-population.php>, <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/ECS/europe-central-asia/fertility-rate>

Table 1 and figure 2 shows the population of 2020 and 2019 of countries/regions of the Europe along with fertility rate and changes in the fertility rate compared to 2019. By studying the table 1 it is visible that almost all the regions fertility rate is less than 2.1 which is stable fertility rate. Few of the countries even faced decline from 2019 to 2020. Countries like France, Germany and Sweden has high fertility rate while places like Moldova, Spain, Greece, Italy has lowest fertility rate.

Fertility Rate in European Countries, 2020

Figure 2 Source: <https://statisticstimes.com/demographics/european-countries-by-population.php>
Europe is a big land mass area located entirely in northern hemisphere occupying about 6.2% of the Earth's land with 10,180,000 Km² (Poulsen, 2020). Europe contributes to 10% of world population that is 747,636,026 according to 2020 censuses (Europe Demographics, 2020). The life expectancy of Europe is nearly 80 years while the fertility rate is 1.5 in some countries and 1.3 in some countries which are

leading to increase in the elder people depending on working population. Hence this is changing the age pyramid of Europe drastically. According to 2019 survey 20% of population is aged 65 and over while up to 6% of population is aged 80 and over. If this trend is continued, aged population of 80 or above will be increased to 15% by 2100 (Population structure and Ageing, 2020). The population between 15 to 65 is said as working population- it is observed that Europe will loss almost 30 million working age by 2050 and that will increase dependency ratio due to the decline in fertility rate.

Causes

According to the studies and survives many factors are found that can be the cause of decline in the fertility around the world although many of them are not certain. These causes can include both the socioeconomic and institutional factors as mentioned below.

- Women empowerment in education is one of the important factors for decreasing fertility rate since increased education level has negative influence on fertility rate. Improved education also promotes other factors such as women's workforce participation, use of contraceptive and health of children etc.
- High child mortality rate slow the population growth with fertility rate. With improvement in health facilities child mortality rates have drastically declined that has promoted decrease in fertility rate since 1950.
- Introduction of safe and accessible contraceptive and family planning resources along with social and cultural norms have sharpen the decline of fertility rates in the Europeans countries.
- Improved prosperity i.e. high income of European Countries has promoted the number of factors that decline the fertility such educational opportunities, employability, changing cultural norms about marriages and health awareness etc. have encouraged the decline in fertility rate.
- The postponing the pregnancy is one of the most important cause – this factor can be the cause of couple working life or women studies for which they want to delay their pregnancy and eventually with the increase in their age leading to decrease their fertility rate. The working women population in Europe is more than 65% which increased rapidly from the past ten years which used to be less than 50% in 2000 (Beaujouan, 2021).
- Better standard of life – even though 65% of women working along with men, many of them have less pay which can be difficult to have high standard of life that lead to decrease the desire of number of children in many families.
- Beside these socioeconomic factors some of the institutional factors can include changing roles of gender due to high competitions, unable to take care of children and market rigidities (Belsia, 2009). Increased divorce can also be said as one of the reason as many countries of Europe have frequent divorce cases. In those the countries with high rate of divorces can be said as Portugal with 64 divorces per 1000 marriages, Luxembourg with 62, and Spain with 57 (Divorce rates in Europe 2017).

Consequences

As the fertility rate declines, problems of aging arises that reduces the working age population size leads slow economic growth that is very difficult to recover the economic growth because of imbalance between working age population and elderly population. On the other, declined fertility rate reduces total population size that decreases burden on natural resources and environment which haves positive social and economic consequences in the country.

Even though decrease in population in the present scenario is good thing but there should be stable decline. Rapid decline can lead to many disadvantages to the country.

- The first and main impact of fertility decline in Europe is leading to increase in the ageing of its population. Present the people aged 65 or above constitutes more that 20% of Europe population

(Population structure and Ageing, 2020). As the fertility decline the young people who will join the workforce is reduced but the retiring people number is increasing.

- Fertility decline can damage the economic growth as depending people are more than the working force. It will be difficult to use the country resources effectively without working labor force (Jonathan Grant, 2005).
- This rapid decline in fertility rate can lead to the start of 5th stage of demographic transition where there will be high death rate than the birth rate (Kiran, 2019).

Polices

Almost all the countries in Europe are facing decline in their fertility rate. In those countries like Spain, Greece, Italy has very less fertility rate from 1.2 to 1.5. So those countries decided to adopt policies like money for birth.

- Spain government decided to adopt Pro-natal policy where newborn can receive 2500 euros. It can financial help families to raise their children and can also encourage people to give births (Spain's Government Sees Folly of Falling Fertility, 2008). Beside this other countries adopted policy of funding money at the time of their growth for their education.
- Paternity Leave- this is to provide leave to the women during their pregnancy. Like Czech Republic paid 70% earning to the women in their maternity leave.
- Providing child care facilities- countries like Germany and France is providing child care facilities especial to the new born which can help the parents where both are in working force (Davies, 2013)

Polices like this can help couples to give more births and there should be combined polices like Gender equality. Gender equality can help in reducing abortions and provide equal opportunities to both the genders in working force.

Discussion

The global fertility rate has been dropped by 50% since 1950 caused by number of socio-economic such as changing demographic composition resulted by due to late marriages, greater use of contraceptives, women's workforce participation etc. However, the global population is increasing while fertility rate is declining resulting from proportion between birth, death and migration ratios in a particular country. Most of the European countries along with remaining economically advanced countries are experiencing low fertility rate. On the other hand, half the world's nation's especially developing and developed countries are still producing larger new generation. There are three major causes for declining fertility rate across the world including deaths in childhood, greater use contraception and women's participation in education and work. The countries which are facing baby bust will experience ageing problems along with decreasing size of population; if there no immigration in these countries in coming future. Therefore age structure of these countries population will be changed. Thus, the demographic composition of the society in these countries will be change in coming future. The demographic change in the population will lead decrease in population size of these countries. The affected countries will have to change the immigration policies for inviting more population from outside because encouraging women for having more children cannot be successful since adopted life style of women in European countries i.e. use contraception and women's higher participation etc.

From the above analysis it is noted that there is rapid change in fertility rate, it declined to 1.5 from 4.2 with in the past few decades. Even many polices came into force the growth is not high. According to Eurostat's if this is continued the aged people 80 or above will be increase to 15% from % percent. And by then Europe will loss more than half of its working force who will be aged to retirement. Then the working force will be very less as the fertility is declining. Lack of working force can lead to decrease in production which in turn damages the economic growth of a country. Temporary solutions like attracting international workers and students can help in increasing productive population if they

permanently settle in the country. But as mentioned it is temporary solution but to control fertility decline there should be encouragement in the native people to give more births. Providing childcare facilities, financial aid, working leaves can help some people to give births. There should be changes in social structure so that abortions and divorces can be reduced. Women who think early pregnancy between 24 to 30 will disturb their studies or working lives should be provided with some facilities that can encourage those women to give births as well as they can continue their dreams after pregnancy. It is observed that high unemployment in young people is also encouraging them to not to have children at young age, so more employment opportunities should be provided to young people which can help them finally for stable family.

Conclusion

“Baby Bust” in the European countries has various social and economic consequences in the region. Most of the reasons for fertility decline is personal decisions which are influenced due to their financial problems and believes of the people about freedom, career dreams and other social problems. Hence government policies providing financial aids is not enough to control the fertility decline. People should be created awareness about the demographic transitions and trends and healthy fertility age so they can understand the problems they can face in future which can encourage for more births in early age because for sustainable growth and economic growth of a country there is a need for stable population.

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